

Weighted Partial Radiation Efficiency and Effective Coverage as Key Performance Indicators for the Analysis of Automotive Antennas

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Abstract— It is essential to characterize the automotive antenna in its installed state because the metallic car body has a significant influence on the antenna's performance. In this connection, the 5GAA has recommended certain key performance indicators (KPIs), such as the Total Radiated Power (TRP), Partial Radiated Power (PRP), etc. for evaluating automotive antennas. However, these KPIs do not adequately reflect the vehicular integration effects on the antenna's performance. In order to fill this gap, two novel KPIs have been proposed in this paper, namely, the weighted Partial Radiation Efficiency and Effective Coverage. The weighting scheme for the calculation of the KPIs has been defined based on direction of importance. To demonstrate their significance, two different vehicular antenna integration topologies have been evaluated employing the KPIs. The results have been compared with existing metrics namely PRP and TRP.

Keywords— autonomous vehicles, automotive antenna, antenna placement, V2X, KPI, 5GAA, ITS

I. INTRODUCTION

The electromagnetic coupling between the metallic car body and the automotive antenna significantly impacts latter's performance. Thus, it is imperative to characterize an automotive antenna in its installed state. Moreover, it is of prime importance to ensure a certain minimum level of performance for the vehicular antennas, especially for safety critical applications, such as, the Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communication. In this respect, the 5GAA has recommended certain key performance indicators (KPIs) such as, the Total Radiated Power (TRP), Partial Radiated Power (PRP), etc. [1]. However, it has been shown in [2] that TRP and PRP are not sufficient to evaluate the vehicular integration effects on the performance of the antenna. The paper demonstrates that across various antenna mounting locations, the values of TRP and PRP are nearly similar. Consequently, relying solely on these KPIs for discrimination may prove inadequate.

In [2], the cumulative distribution function (CDF) of the Effective Isotropic Radiated Power (EIRP) has been suggested as a metric to characterize the integration effects on the antenna. Specifically, the EIRP value at 60% CDF has been recommended as the KPI. However, for automotive communications, defining an acceptable value based on a percentile threshold might not necessarily reflect the actual communication requirements. This is mainly because vehicular communications occur within specific regions of the 3D spherical coordinate system [1]. Consequently, the objective should revolve around upholding optimal antenna performance across the entirety of said region, as opposed to a percentage thereof. Furthermore, the EIRP value at 60% CDF as a distinguishing factor for automotive antennas is very specific to the scenario examined in the paper. Thereby making it challenging to generalize the KPI for comparing different antenna positions in different car geometries.

In [3], the authors have characterized the impact of the car body on the antenna by calculating the statistical deviation of the antenna gain pattern when it was installed in a car as compared to its gain pattern in free-space conditions. While this KPI provides an insight into assessing the vehicular integration effects, it does not furnish information regarding whether such deviation leads to an improvement or deterioration in the antenna's performance. Therefore, novel KPIs are needed to be defined for characterizing automotive antennas.

II. NOVEL KPI FOR AUTOMOTIVE ANTENNA EVALUATION

In this paper, two new KPIs are proposed for evaluating vehicular antennas, namely, the weighted Partial Radiation Efficiency and the Effective Coverage. The primary emphasis of this work centers around the V2X communication, as it is one of the most essential safety critical communication system for cars. However, the proposed KPIs can also be adopted for other automotive communication applications such as Vehicle-to-network (V2N) etc. Before delving into the detailed formalism of the proposed KPIs, it is essential to emphasize on the direction of importance for the V2X communication.

In [4], it has been demonstrated that the forward and backward directions of the car's driving orientation could be more critical in terms of minimum required antenna gain for V2X communication as illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1 Top view of a car model showing the azimuthal regions of importance for V2X communication. The driving direction is along the positive x axis. The numbers 1-4 have been used to demarcate the four sectors

As can be seen in the figure, $\Delta\phi = 104^\circ$ is adopted for the sector angles in the front and back directions of the car. This choice adheres to the recommended upper bound for the azimuthal angle of arrival spread in V2X communication [5]. On the other hand, in case of the elevation angle, the region of importance is limited to $80^\circ \leq \theta \leq 100^\circ$ [1].

In the next subsections, the two proposed KPIs are defined.

A. Weighted Partial Radiation Efficiency

In the context of any given application, the primary objective of an antenna is to maximize the radiated power towards the intended regions while minimizing it in undesired directions. In order to quantify this crucial aspect of the transmitting antenna, the KPI Partial Radiation Efficiency (η_p) is defined here as:

$$\eta_p = \frac{\text{PRP in the region of interest}}{\text{TRP}} \quad (1)$$

In (1), considering the entire azimuthal range (i.e., $0^\circ \leq \phi \leq 360^\circ$) as the region of interest would lead to the omission of azimuthal directional information within η_p . Hence, this would diminish the utility of η_p in effectively characterizing automotive antennas. Therefore, the η_p should be calculated individually in the four sectors shown in Fig.1, with $80^\circ \leq \theta \leq 100^\circ$. Consequently, this results in four distinct η_p values. To condense these multiple η_p into a single KPI, the weighted η_p is hereby defined as:

$$\eta_p|_{\text{weighted}} = w_1 \cdot \eta_{p,1} + w_2 \cdot \eta_{p,2} + w_3 \cdot \eta_{p,3} + w_4 \cdot \eta_{p,4} \quad (2)$$

where $\eta_{p,1}$, $\eta_{p,2}$, $\eta_{p,3}$ and $\eta_{p,4}$ denotes the η_p values calculated in sectors 1 to 4 respectively. The w_1 , w_2 , w_3 and w_4 denotes their corresponding weights. For simplicity, the total weight (i.e., $\sum_{i=1}^4 w_i$) is considered to be 1. The numerical value of the individual weights correspond to the importance of the respective sector. Since, both the front and back directions are equally important for V2X as mentioned in [4], the corresponding weights are taken to be equal (i.e., $w_1 = w_3$). Following the symmetry, the weights of the left and right sectors are also considered to be equal (i.e., $w_2 = w_4$).

The weights can be quantified based on the benchmark desired by the antenna engineer. A more rigorous weighting approach can be undertaken by involving an in-depth analysis of the channel model and incorporating the signal arrival probability as weights. However, the detailed analysis of V2X channel model is out of the scope of this paper. Nevertheless, it is crucial to ensure that the weighted η_p efficiently discriminates between an optimum antenna effectively radiating in the region of interest and a subpar antenna. For illustrative purpose, in this work the weights are chosen as:

$$\begin{aligned} w_1 &= w_3 = 0.45 \\ w_2 &= w_4 = 0.05 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Put simply, (3) implies that 90% emphasis is allocated towards the front and back of the driving direction of the car, with the remaining 10% allocated to the left and right directions. The weighted η_p , being an efficiency based KPI, can be expressed in dB. Thus, its value ranges between $-\infty$ dB to 0 dB, with 0 dB denoting the ideal best case scenario, where the antenna efficiently emits its entire power within the region of interest.

B. Weighted Effective coverage

The coverage of an antenna pertains to the region in 3D space where it can effectively establish communication with other antennas. In the context of 5G mm-wave beamforming antennas, this is gauged by the KPI known as 'spherical coverage' [6]. It is defined in relation to the CDF of the EIRP, for e.g., EIRP at 50% CDF for mobile phone at FR2 frequency bands. However, at sub-6 GHz V2X frequency, the communication takes place within a certain region in the spherical coordinate system [1]. Hence, the assessment of the antenna should consider its performance across the entire region of interest, rather than evaluating only a certain percentage of the whole sphere. Thus, the approach mentioned in [6] cannot be used directly in case of sub-6 GHz V2X communication. In this regard, the coverage can be alternatively defined from the perspective of receiving antenna, based on the sensitivity of its receiver. In light of this, a new KPI is hereby introduced, termed the Effective Coverage (EC).

The gain of the installed antenna varies significantly in different directions based on antenna locations and car geometry. Thus, it can be represented in terms of probability distribution. Consequently, the EC can be defined as the probability that the antenna gain in the region of interest is greater than the minimum required gain for effective communication. This can be formulated as:

$$EC = P(G_{\text{antenna}} \geq G_{\text{threshold}}) \quad (4)$$

where the symbol P denotes the probability function, G_{antenna} denotes the antenna gain at a particular spherical coordinate within the region of interest and $G_{\text{threshold}}$ denotes the minimum antenna gain required to prevent outage. The calculation of the $G_{\text{threshold}}$ in (4) is straightforward utilizing the link budget formulation and incorporating the receiver sensitivity value. Alternatively, the EC can be viewed as the complementary CDF (i.e., $1 - \text{CDF}$) of the minimum threshold antenna gain required to sustain communication.

Fig.2 (Top left) Antenna locations for AIT-1, (Top right) Antenna locations for AIT-2, (Bottom left) Radiation pattern due to AIT-1 and (Bottom right) radiation pattern due to AIT-2.

Similar to η_p , as discussed in the previous subsection, the process of deriving a meaningful conclusion about antenna coverage for the V2X application involves calculating the EC separately within the four distinct sectors. In the next step, the individual EC s are combined into a single weighted EC as:

$$EC|_{\text{weighted}} = w_1 \cdot EC_1 + w_2 \cdot EC_2 + w_3 \cdot EC_3 + w_4 \cdot EC_4 \quad (5)$$

where, EC_1, EC_2, EC_3 and EC_4 are the effective coverage values in sectors 1 to 4 of Fig.1. The assigned weights, (i.e., w_1, w_2, w_3 and w_4) correspond to the values outlined in (3). The weighted EC is unitless, as it is based on probability. Hence its value ranges between 0 to 1, with 1 denoting the best case scenario implying that the directional gain distribution of the antenna is optimum to cover the entire region of interest.

III. DEMONSTRATION OF THE PROPOSED KPIS USING SIMPLE CAR MODEL

To demonstrate their utility, two antenna integration topologies (AITs) are compared using a simple car model. In each of the AITs, two Hertzian dipole antennas (operating at 5.9 GHz) are placed $\lambda/4$ away from car chassis. Their radiation patterns have been combined using the maximal ratio combining (MRC) technique. The antenna locations for both the AITs along with the corresponding 3D radiation patterns are presented in Fig.2. For both the AITs, the antennas are assumed to be lossless.

Additionally, in this section, the proposed KPIS are compared with the existing metrics namely PRP and TRP.

A. Link Budget

In this study, the threshold gain ($G_{threshold}$) for the computation of weighted EC has been determined through the utilization of a geometry-based stochastic channel model, as described in [5]. This is mainly due to the inherent limitation of simple channel models like the free space path loss model in accurately representing path loss within V2X channels [5]. Furthermore, within the scope of scenarios outlined by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI), primary emphasis is placed on the urban scenario in the link budget assessment of this work. This preference is attributed to the urban environment's elevated complexity, arising from substantial obstructions and scattering due to buildings and vehicles. The path loss equation for urban scenario is as follows [5]:

$$PL = 38.77 + 16.7 \log(d) + 18.2 \log(f_c) \quad (6)$$

where, PL is the path loss in dB, d is the distance in meters and f_c is the frequency in GHz [5]. Here, d is taken to be 500 m and f_c is 5.9 GHz. Additionally, to incorporate the shadowing due to other vehicles in urban scenario, the log-normal shadowing with a standard deviation, i.e., $\sigma=5.3$ dB (as mentioned in [5]) has been added to (6). The link budget equation used here is as follows:

$$G_{threshold} = P_{Rx} - EIRP_{Tx} + PL \quad (7)$$

where, $G_{threshold}$ is the required minimum gain of the receiving antenna, P_{Rx} is the receiver sensitivity, $EIRP_{Tx}$ is EIRP of the transmitting antenna and PL is the path loss as defined in (6).

For the link budget calculation, the $EIRP_{Tx}$ is assumed to be 33 dBm, based on its maximum limit as mentioned in [7]. The receiver sensitivity (i.e., P_{Rx}) is chosen to be -85 dBm, based on its value mentioned in [8] for BPSK modulation at 3 Mbits/sec data rate. In order to incorporate the random shadowing effect, the link budget computation was carried out 10,000 times in a loop and in 99% of the cases, the maximum value of the required $G_{threshold}$ was found to be 2 dBi.

B. Evaluation of KPIS

During transmission, the individual antennas within each AIT radiates independently. This leads to the evaluation of the weighted η_p for individual antennas within its corresponding AIT using (1-3). On the contrary, the weighted EC is calculated considering the MRC radiation patterns of Fig.2 using (4-5). In order to calculate the EC , at first the complementary CDF of the gain values in the four sectors have been determined. The plot of complementary CDF vs antenna gain for both the AITs are shown Fig.3. For the ease of readability, a vertical line denoting the threshold gain of 2 dBi has been added in the plots. The value of the complementary CDF at 2 dBi is the value of EC in that particular sector.

The computed values of TRP, PRP, weighted η_p and weighted EC of the two AITs are presented in Table I. From the table, it can be observed that the TRP and PRP are similar for both the AITs. However, the weighted η_p and EC of AIT-2 are significantly greater than AIT-1. Thus, the KPIS proposed here efficiently highlight the improved alignment of the radiation pattern of AIT-2 towards the more critical directions. This can also be verified from the radiation patterns in Fig.2.

Fig.3. Plot of Complementary CDF vs Antenna Gain within $80^\circ \leq \theta \leq 100^\circ$ for (a.) AIT-1 and (b.) AIT-2.

TABLE I. EVALUATION OF AITs

KPIs	AIT-1		AIT-2	
	Dipole 1	Dipole 2	Dipole 1	Dipole 2
TRP (dBm)	33	33	33	33
PRP (dBm) ¹	27.2	27.2	27.6	27.6
Weighted η_p (dB)	-12.6	-12.6	-9.6	-9.6
Weighted EC (of the MRC pattern)	0.55		0.94	

¹ PRP has been calculated in the angular range: $80^\circ \leq \theta \leq 100^\circ, 0^\circ \leq \phi \leq 360^\circ$ [1].

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, two novel KPIs have been introduced for evaluating automotive antennas, namely, the weighted partial radiation efficiency and effective coverage. To underscore their significance, the proposed KPIs have been compared to existing metrics such as PRP and TRP. It has been observed that the integration effects of the automotive antenna can be more effectively evaluated using the KPIs proposed in this paper. These KPIs offer potential utility in the homologation process for semi-autonomous and fully-autonomous vehicles. Additionally, they can serve as objective functions within machine learning algorithms, offering the prospect of automating antenna selection and integration processes. The future work will involve the validation of these KPIs through virtual drive testing.

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